

STUDY OF THE MANAGEMENT SKILL OF THE HEADMASTERS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL IN NANDED CITY

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Introduction :-

Headmaster is the chief person in the management of the school. "The headmaster holds the lye position in a school as the captain of the ship holds the key position on a ship" W.M. Raiburn. There is an important role of headmaster in the school management. Planning communicating, motivating, organizing etc are the area of the work of the headmaster.

Headmaster is responsible for administrative management, it is about managing information through student, teachers and society. "Evidence of good administration is when you don't know it is happening!" The lord piston of Mile End. Many administrative and managerial processes are repetitive and require to be regularly reviewed; school management is also one of such processes.

A good headmaster can add value to the school management by challenging the efficiency and reliability of procedures that have been running for continuing improvement and identifying and cutting out any outdate practices. With the speed of change in business today the headmaster has to value the people who are expected to operate complex problems.

"The destiny of India is now being shaped in her classrooms." Dr.Kothari ,the role of headmaster is to give the student 'The art of living' harmoniously and developing ideals and values needed in an enlightened citizen of a democratic and secular state.

Statement of the problem

"Study of the management skill of the secondary school headmasters in Nanded city"

Definitions of the terms

01. Secondary School :

Secondary schools are such schools where students study the curriculum programme needed for the secondary school certificate examination or equivalent examinations.

02. Management :

Management is concerned with seeing that the job gets done, its tasks are centered on planning and guiding the operations that are going on in the enterprise

03. Management skill :

01. The act, manner or practice of managing, handling, supervision or control, of the working people.
02. Skill in managing ; executive ability

04. Headmaster:

Head person in the secondary school who looks the educational management and administration.

Objective of the study

To study the management skill of the headmasters of the secondary school in Nanded city.

Assumptions of the study

1. Headmasters of the secondary school in Nanded city are well educated.
2. Headmasters of the secondary school in Nanded city know school management work
3. Headmasters of the secondary school in Nanded city are from the different layer of the society.

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Scope of the study

In the present study 18 granted Marathi medium schools and 4 English medium schools are included.

Limitations of the study

Present study is limited to the secondary schools of Marathi and English medium in Nanded city.

Design of the Study

Research procedure :

Research procedure is selected according to the objectives of the study.

- The researcher has selected the survey method of investigation for the present study.

Sampling :

The present research study is a sampling study. In this study observations are made of a limited number of sample of the head masters of secondary schools in Nanded city.

- 18 secondary schools of Marathi Medium.
- 4 secondary schools of English medium.

are included in the study. There is 25% sample of both medium's schools.

Tools of the study:-

Depending upon the nature of information to be collected, researcher selected the valid tests in the present investigation. Management skill test is used for data collection

The test is scientific, valid and world wide used. Test is, available on the web site of the quondam test this test is online test.

Data analysis' and interpretation :

Mean is used in the present study, for the data interpretation.

Mean

$$M = \frac{\sum FX}{N}$$

N

M= Mean, F= frequency, X= gated number

N= Total Number

Data Interpretation

Mean Of the Management Skill Of The Headmasters Of Secondary Schools

Management Skill	Frequency (F)	Test No. (X)
62	4	248
61	1	61
60	1	60
58	3	174
57	2	114
55	2	110
54	1	54
51	1	51
50	3	150
49	1	49
47	3	147
	N=22	FX=1212

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(Mean)} \quad M &= \frac{\text{SFX}}{N} \\ &= \frac{1212}{22} \\ \text{Mean} &= 55.09 \end{aligned}$$

Conclusion:-

Conclusions in general

In the light of analysis and interpretation, of the data the researcher has given following conclusions.

- The mean of management skill of the head masters of the secondary school in Nanded city is 55.
- In the studied sample management skill of the 40% head masters is more than 59 and 18% head masters management skill is less than 50.

BIBALIOGRAPHY

- Best John. W. and Khan James U. Research in Education, (1998) Prontice_Hall of India Private Ltd. New Delhi.
- Pandit Bansi Bihari Shikshanshastratil sanshodhan (1998) Nutan Prakashan Pune
- Dr. Arvind Dunakhe Shalay Vyavasthapan Prashasan, Sanghatan, Niyojan 2007 Nitya Nutan Prakashan, Pune
- Parasanis N.R. Bharatiy Shaikshanic Niyojan Nutan Prakashan Pune
- Tamhankar S.D. Shaikshanic Prashasan, Niyojan Nutan Prakashan Pune.
- Marcin Hughes, L.Bonita Patterson, James Bradford Terrell Emotional intelligence in Action Traning and coaching activities for leaders and managers. (2006)
- Dr. Dam Matzke Emotional intelligence Successful Personality (2007)

- Dalip Singh Emotional Intelligence at Work; A professional guide.
- D.Goleman Emotional Intelligence Bantam, 1995
- Azarum M.,The Relationship between emotional intelligence and problem solving method with general health, Tabriz University; 2004
- Sandy Golber Emotional Intelligence in seventh gradestudents, Viterbo University

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